

Crop Prediction Using KNN Algorithm

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Abstract—A crucial choice is machine learning is assistance program for crop forecasting, comprising encouraging choices on which crops to plant on various geographical and climatic situations. Several use of machine learning algorithms has been bolster crop forecasting. Agricultural production is biological, economic, and seasonal factors causes. The second-largest population is in India, country in the globe, with the bulk of its citizens, India's primary industry is agriculture. Farmers consistently plant the same crops without attempting novel crop varieties, they are using random amounts of fertilizers without being aware of the inadequate quantity and content. So, this has an immediate impact on crop productivity and also destroys the top and increases soil acidity. So, KNN is used to construct a system for farmers' benefit. The application will suggest the most suitable crop for a specific situation based on various types of soil and weather parameters. Consequently, by using our application farmers can grow a wider range of crops and possibly possible profit margin growth.

Keywords--KNN algorithm, crop prediction, Machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The state's economy depends heavily on agriculture, therefore increasing production in this industry is crucial for a more inclusive progress. Demand for agricultural land has increased over time due to reasons including industrialization, urbanization, housing, infrastructure, and other issues. Such circumstances lead to the conversion of agricultural land to commercial use. The amount of cultivable land that can expand is drastically decreasing, which has a negative impact on the amount of net fields that can be sown. A region's crop must be predicted in advance depending on the weather and other factors that increase productivity. This will aid farmers in making crop decisions or enhancing the output of their particular crops in the area. The relationship between soil characteristics, humidity, temperature, and rainfall is crucial for increasing crop output. One of the finest methods for forecasting unknowable quantities is machine learning. Using

machine learning, this approach regulates agricultural yield expectations. This application's evaluations assist farmers in predicting the appropriate crop for a specific field by using a real dataset that includes rainfall, temperature, humidity, and soil factors like amount of nitrogen, phosphorus, and pH. Prediction methods include Support Vector Machine (SVM), Regression analysis, K Nearest Neighbor (KNN) and a variety of others. In this work, KNN is utilized. On the basis of the data set that contains observations of the known category, classification in machine learning is the process of determining to which group of categories a new object or observation belongs. KNN is a non-parametric algorithm for language learning. In order to predict the classification of another instance, a model where information emphasis is clustered into a few groups is used. The KNN algorithm is dependent on the feature's closeness: Following our training set, how strongly out of test highlights impact how we handle a particular point of data. KNN is a classification tool that can be used. The vote of an element is distributed among its closest neighbors to the most regular class, with the entity being distinguished by a higher percentage of those neighbors' votes. This computation represents an average of the "estimates of" k from its closest neighbors. Euclidean distance is a frequent metric for measuring distance in KNN algorithms. With the use of this method, crop predictions can be made more precisely. Predicting the harvest in advance based on the specific conditions necessary for a healthy crop yield is the major goal of the endeavor.

II. RELATED WORKS

In the existing system crops are cultivated according to rainfall, temperature, humidity and soil moisture. So it does not provide accurate prediction of crops for different lands.

In the agriculture industry, a lot of work has been done and numerous ML algorithms have been used. Increasing farm output and providing it to consumers at the best price and quality is the largest issue in agriculture. Additionally, it has been noted that at least 50% of farm food is lost and never consumed. The suggested approach offers suggestions for reducing farm produce waste. A model where the crop is predicted using KNN algorithms by creating clusters is shown in one of the more recent papers. KNN clustering has been

demonstrated to perform significantly better than SVM or regression. [3].

The main actions done to improve agriculture comprise integrating technological know-how and innovations to make the agricultural industry more proficient and straightforward for farmers by anticipating the ideal crops using all ML techniques. The advantages of several methods, including ANN, Fuzzy Networks, and data mining approaches, are discussed in the paper. [5].

Another significant piece of research evaluates the soil's quality and forecasts crop yields along with an appropriate fertilizer recommendation [4]. This model's inputs included the pH value and the user-provided location. An API was utilized to forecast the weather and temperature for the current location. The system compares the outcomes of supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods.

One of the initial projects created a specific webpage to evaluate how meteorological conditions affect crop productivity in the designated Madhya Pradesh districts [2]. The neighborhoods were chosen based on the area where the crop was grown. Using these standards as a guide, the top five districts with the largest crop area was selected and the study focused on the dominant crops in the chosen districts. The crops chosen included wheat, soybeans, corn, and paddy, whose yield during a continuous 20-day period was years of experience were tallied. The precision of the selected model, the range was 76% to 90% crops with an 82% accuracy on average.

A classifier that forecasts the crop using a greedy technique in [1], yield was proposed. Using a decision tree classifier, an attribute has been demonstrated to produce superior outcomes. An ensemble model put forth recommends incorporating the influences of different models, which has consistently been demonstrated to be better than each model alone. ensemble of random forests, multiple decision tree models are used in classification to forecast the crop output The information is divided into two sets, such as training data, test data, with a ratio of 67% to 33%, and data, with which it is calculated what the mean and standard deviation. Also, this work utilizes grouping similar crops together to maximize yield accurate outcomes.

III. METHODOLOGY

Fig_1 Process flow

A. DATASETS

For the data sets from the specified region, the suggested model forecasts the crop. The data sets required for various crops are gathered from the web. Temperature, humidity, soil characteristics, and rainfall are significant crop-determining factors in the data. The aforementioned elements are present in the samples. The KNN algorithm is employed to categories and forecast the ideal crop. The values of every available data set are used as input variables for crop prediction. The remaining data sets are used for testing, while the majority of the available data sets are used for training. For crop prediction, the KNN algorithm is a machine learning technique.

B. LEARNING ALGORITHM

A data mining method known as the k-nearest neighbor (KNN) method is regarded as one of the top five methods. With the aid of the qualities of the existing variables, it achieves the characteristics of the new variable. Both classification and regression issues can benefit from it. It makes an effort to describe a mysterious case based on the recognized description of its neighbors. Give us an opportunity to believe that the alleged preparation set, which consists of numerous tests with accomplished grouping, is available. Naturally, each example should be organized in relation to the instances that surround it. With this approach, if an instance's order is ever in doubt, it can usually be predicted at that point by examining the ordering of its nearest neighbor tests. In the context of an obscure example and a set of preparations, each of the distinctions between the obscure example and each of the cases in the collection can be comprehended. The instance in the preparation that is closest to the own sample unidentifiable is contrasted to the division with the lowest regard. Therefore, depending on how this closest neighbor is described, the obscure example might be arranged. As a result, when using the KNN algorithm to predict crops, the factors that are closest to a given point (the crop), such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, and soil parameters, are taken into account. If these variables have enough values, then the crop will likely produce a good yield, depending on the other variables. The steps listed below can be used to implement KNN:

- 1) Open the data set.
- 2) Set the "k" value.
- 3) To obtain the predicted class, repeat the training data set's numbers from 1 to all of them.
- 4) Calculate the separation between each line of training data and the test data. (In this case, the Euclidean distance is used because it is the most often used method.)

- 5) Sort the calculated distances according to their values in ascending order.
- 6) Get the first "k" rows from the categorized array.
- 7) Select the line with the longest continuous class.
- 8) Provide the expected class.

KNN has a few other uses in addition to grouping tools like the one shown above. It is common in applications for pursuit. KNN computation is ideal, for instance, if one has to find the records that are most similar to a certain report, such as when recognizing copyright. The calculation is also widely used in data mining and artificial intelligence. K Nearest Neighbor is particularly useful for detecting anomalies. It is the distinguishing evidence of instances, circumstances, or perceptions that do not match the norm or other items in a collection.

C. PREDICTION OF CROP USING KNN

An overview of the K-NN approach for crop early forecasting is provided in this system. Using K-NN analysis, the unknown parameter is predicted from the known parameters. Although there are many other factors that can be taken into account, in this study we are focusing on the input parameters of rainfall, temperature, humidity, and soil parameters, which are the crucial factors to take into account for a successful harvest. It is possible to predict the unknown crop from the nearest known values of its closest neighbors by computing the Euclidean distance between them. We could then predict crops based on rainfall, temperature, humidity, and soil characteristics. Numerous distance functions, of which the Euclidean distance function is the most popular, can be used to calculate the separation between points in a feature space. Consider x and y to be feature vector representations. The Euclidean metric is typically used to compute the distance between x and y. If $a=(a_1, a_2)$ and $b=(b_1, b_2)$, the distance is given by

$$d(a, b) = \sqrt{(b_1 - a_1)^2 + (b_2 - a_2)^2}$$

The main goal of this implementation is to demonstrate how, when the required input parameters are provided, it aids in crop prediction. The table below presents a portion of the training data.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
NITROGEN	PHOSPHORUS	POTASSIUM	TEMPERATURE	HUMIDITY	PH	RAINFALL	CROP
90	42	43	21	82	6.5	203	rice
85	58	41	22	80	7.0	227	rice
60	55	44	23	82	7.8	264	rice
74	35	40	26	80	7.0	243	rice
78	42	42	20	82	7.6	263	rice
69	37	42	23	83	7.1	251	rice
69	55	38	23	83	5.7	271	rice
94	53	40	20	83	5.7	242	rice
89	54	38	25	84	6.7	230	rice

Fig_1. Data Set Table

Utilizing variables including rainfall, temperature, humidity, and various mineral contents in the soil, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, pH and potassium, the KNN algorithm's output is produced after the data has been input. The dataset is initially loaded, and then the data are trained and tested within it.

Fig_2. User Interface

The crop for a certain location is then predicted using the KNN algorithm once the dataset has been examined.

Fig_3. Result

The inputted values are assessed using the prior dataset and the resultant output, which is the anticipated crop for that particular plot of land. The KNN accurately predicted the crop for the area with an accuracy of roughly 90.46%.

IV. CONCLUSION

A machine learning algorithm to forecast precise crop suggestions for specific lands. Agriculture is a crucial industry that contributes to a nation's economic growth. Therefore, it's critical that farmers are able to produce the highest possible agricultural production. To boost agricultural productivity, many machine learning approaches are used in agriculture. K-

NN offers a reasonable level of accuracy for predicting agricultural productivity. The suggested model is supported by the carefully crafted data set and the machine learning technique. Using the information gathered, the system will forecast the crop that will grow best on a specific piece of land. This forecast will aid farmers in choosing the crop to plant in order to obtain a higher yield in each year, enhancing economic development and overall crop productivity.

V. REFERENCES

- [1]. Priya P, Muthaiah U, Balamurugan M, "Predicting yield of the crop using machine learning algorithm", International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology, 2018
- [2]. Veenadhari S, Misra B, Singh CD, "Machine learning approach for forecasting crop yield based on climatic parameters", 2014
- [3]. S. Pavani, Augusta Sophy Beulet P., "Heuristic Prediction of Crop Yield Using Machine Learning Technique", International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), December 2019
- [4]. Ghadge R, Kulkarni J, More P, Nene S, Priya RL, "Prediction of crop yield using machine learning", Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol. (IRJET), 2018
- [5]. Sriram Rakshith.K, Dr.Deepak.G, Rajesh M, Sudharshan K S, Vasanth S, Harish Kumar N, "A Survey on Crop Prediction using Machine Learning Approach", In International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET), 2019